

FEATURES OF DETERMINING INDICATORS OF OPERATING ACTIVITY IN EVALUATING THE ECONOMIC SECURITY OF ENTERPRISE

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The article reveals the essence of indicators of operating activity: financial safety margin and operating leverage as important indicators of economic security of enterprise. They characterize the main activity of an economic entity. There were identified four levels of economic security: critical, low, medium and high levels. Corresponding formulas were determined. There was determined the level of riskiness of production and economic security by the example of an agricultural enterprise in the Republic of Moldova. Proposed method can be applied in practice to control the production process, cost structure and to increase efficiency and economic security of the enterprise as a whole.

JEL Classification: M11, D20

Keywords: economic security, break-even point, financial safety margin, operating leverage

Enterprise represents an open dynamic system, which operates in conditions of environment instability and under the influence of numerous factors. As it was noted by Hindle and Klyver, in advanced economies, during the first five years, the attrition rate of new businesses varies „from around 80 per cent to around 50 per cent of the original cohort” [1, p. 205]. In this regard, the issues of ensuring economic security become particularly important.

V.F.Gaponenko considered economic security to be a condition of enterprise, which is characterized by its ability to properly function to achieve its goals and their change, within certain limits, under existing external conditions [2]. Ensuring economic security is the basis of sustainable operation and

development of the economic entity. The economic security of enterprise represents a state that characterizes the ability of an economic entity to ensure efficient use of resources and entrepreneurial opportunities to prevent possible threats, ensure stable functioning and achieve business objectives.

In determining the level of economic security of enterprise, special attention should be paid to its main activity – production. The study of features of calculating indicators of operating activity: break-even point, financial safety margin and operating leverage, becomes increasingly important as the analysis of these values can assist enterprises in making right decisions.

The purpose of this article is to present a method of determining break-even point,

financial safety margin and operating leverage as indicators of the level of an enterprise's economic security.

Methodology

In order to achieve the purpose of this study, there were carried out an analysis of scientific literature and enterprises data, and determined the dependency between economic security of enterprise and indicators of operating activities such as: break-even point, financial safety margin and operating leverage.

Results and discussion

The economic security of the enterprise is directly related to profitability, which is seen as a prerequisite for a sustainable

$$q_{min} = \frac{FC}{p - AVC} \quad (1)$$

where: FC - fixed costs;

p - price per unit;

AVC - average variable costs, lei/q.

There should be paid a special attention to the cost structure, especially to the level of fixed costs, which have a significant impact on the profit.

The analysis of the financial safety margin provides a more objective assessment of the

$$D = \frac{q - q_{min}}{q} * 100 \% \quad (2)$$

where: q - the actual yield, q/ha.

This indicator shows how much sales level can fall before a business reaches its break-even point, starts to lose money or stops making a profit. A high financial safety margin ensures more opportunities to

development. In plant growing important conditions for achieving the profitability are managing the costs and obtaining high values of crop yields. For this purpose, it is necessary to calculate the break-even point for determining the volume of production that ensures equality between sales revenue and total cost of production. Where actual production volume is below the break-even point, the production becomes unprofitable, but in the opposite case, the enterprise will obtain profit, and thus will have the opportunity to develop [3]. The break-even point (q_{min}) can be determined by the equation:

economic security of enterprise. The financial safety margin indicates the level of actual production in terms of its critical value. A relative indicator of financial safety margin (D) is calculated as follows:

preserve profits in case of revenue decrease, and this positively affects the economic security of the enterprise.

Another indicator that reflects the condition of economic security of an enterprise is the operating leverage (L). This indicator

represents the mechanism of control of the enterprise's profit, through the optimization

$$L = \frac{\Delta Pr}{\Delta N} \quad (3)$$

where: ΔPr - the growth of gross profit;
 ΔN - the growth of revenue.

Formula of determining operating leverage may be also represented as follows:

$$L = 1 + \frac{FC}{Pr} \quad (4)$$

The operating leverage shows how many percentage points the profit of the enterprise will change with a change in revenue by one percentage point. Operating leverage characterizes the degree of an enterprise's business risk. The profit of an enterprise, whose level of operating leverage is higher, is more sensitive to changes in sales revenues. An enterprise with a higher level of operating leverage is considered to be of

of the ratio of fixed to variable costs:

higher risk. The enterprise's activity with low operating leverage is associated with lower risk, but also with smaller remuneration or net profit [4].

On the basis of formulas (2) and (4), there were calculated and presented in Figure 1 indicators of the financial safety margin and operating leverage in the production of wheat at the enterprise „Iri-Carmen” SRL in the Republic of Moldova.

Fig. 1. Indicators of the safety margin and operating leverage in the production of wheat at „Iri-Carmen” SRL in 2016.

Source: developed based on the forms 7 and 9 AIC of „Iri-Carmen” SRL, 2016.

The analyzed indicators show the level of economic security of the main activity (production) of an enterprise. The graph of break-even points may indicate the level of

economic security of production of certain crops, as presented in Figure 2 using the example of production of wheat at „Iri-Carmen” SRL (2016).

Fig. 2. Indicators of the break-even point
 (by the example of production of wheat at „Iri-Carmen” SRL, 2016)
 Source: developed based on the forms 7 and 9 AIC of „Iri-Carmen” SRL, 2016

By analogy with the method of determining the level of economic security of production, based on the values of break-even point, we considered the indicators of financial safety margin (Figure 3). There are four levels of economic security of operating component: critical, low, medium, and high.

Fig. 3. Indicators of financial safety margin point
 (by the example of production of wheat at „Iri-Carmen” SRL, 2016)
 Source: developed based on the forms 7 and 9 AIC of „Iri-Carmen” SRL, 2016

The indicators of operating leverage in the production of wheat at „Iri-Carmen” SRL (2016) are presented in Figure 4.

Fig.4. Indicators of operating leverage point
 (by the example of production of wheat at „Iri-Carmen” SRL, 2016)
 Source: developed based on the forms 7 and 9 AIC of „Iri-Carmen” SRL, 2016)

At the critical level, the revenue received from product sales does not cover total costs of the production. This level shows the riskiness of the business.

The enterprise is characterized by a low level of security when it reaches the intersection point of the curves of revenues

and fixed costs (point „A”). The enterprise receives revenues from sales that cover fixed costs, while variable costs remain uncovered, and therefore the enterprise suffers losses. Point „A” on the graph can be determined by the following equation:

$$N = FC \quad (5)$$

where: N - the product sales revenue.

It follows from this that production volume at the point „A”, that is, the critical production volume (q_{cr}), can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} q_{cr} * p &= FC \\ q_{cr} &= \frac{FC}{p} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Knowing the critical production volume, the level of financial safety margin can be calculated at the point „A” by the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} D &= \frac{q - q_{min}}{q} \\ D_{cr} &= \frac{q_{cr} - q_{min}}{q_{cr}} = \frac{\frac{FC}{p} - \frac{FC}{p - AVC}}{\frac{FC}{p}} = 1 - \frac{FC \cdot p}{FC \cdot (p - AVC)} = 1 - \frac{p}{p - AVC} = \frac{AVC}{AVC - p} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{p}{AVC}}; D_{cr} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{p}{AVC}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Based on Equations 4 and 5, it is proposed the operating leverage at the point „A” can be identified by:

$$L_{cr} = 1 + \frac{FC}{P_r} = 1 + \frac{FC}{N - FC - VC} = 1 + \frac{N}{N - N - VC} = 1 - \frac{p \cdot q}{AVC \cdot q} = 1 - \frac{p}{AVC}; L_{cr} = 1 - \frac{p}{AVC} \quad (8)$$

The range of the graph between points „A” and „B” represents the **law level** of security. Point „B” on the graph represents the break-even point (Equation 1). The enterprise covers all its costs, but it still does not receive any profit. The value of the financial safety margin and operating leverage in the break-even point (point „B”) is zero. After reaching the break-even point, the enterprise begins to profit with each subsequent unit of production. The range of the graph between points „B” and „C”

represents the **medium level** of security. The higher the value of the financial safety margin, the more sustainable is the activity of the enterprise.

Once the break-even point is achieved, the profit grows faster than sales volume. The closer is the actual volume of production and sales in relation to their critical volumes, the smaller is the amount of profit and, therefore, the greater is the force of the operating leverage. Even a slight drop in sales can cause a substantial drop in profit.

Reaching point „C” ensures a **high level** of security for the enterprise. This is the level to which enterprises should strive. The enterprises need profit for further

development, that is, to receive return on sales. Accordingly, we suggest to define point „C” on the basis of return on sales (R):

$$R = \frac{Pr}{N} \quad (9)$$

$$R = \frac{Pr}{N} = \frac{q \cdot p - AVC \cdot q - FC}{q \cdot p} = 1 - \frac{AVC \cdot q + FC}{q \cdot p}$$

$$q \cdot p \cdot (1 - R) - AVC \cdot q = FC$$

where: Pr - the gross profit.

It follows that the equation for production volume can take the following form:

$$q = \frac{FC}{q(1-R)-AVC} \quad (10)$$

It is considered that the normative value of return on sales is 0.2. Thus, the volume of production and sales at the point „C” can be determined by the equation:

$$q_o = \frac{FC}{0.8 \cdot p - AVC} \quad (11)$$

where: q_o - the optimal volume of production.

The optimal volume of production represents the volume of products, which provides sales that allow enterprises to receive the necessary profit for further development, that is, to reach a return on sales.

Applying Equations 2 and 10, the financial safety margin at point „C” can be calculated as follows:

$$D = \frac{q - q_{min}}{q} = \frac{\frac{FC}{q(1-R)-AVC} - \frac{FC}{p-AVC}}{\frac{FC}{q(1-R)-AVC}} = \frac{FC \cdot p - FC \cdot p \cdot (1-R)}{(q(1-R)-AVC) \cdot (p-AVC)} \cdot \frac{q(1-R)-AVC}{FC} = \frac{p \cdot R}{p-AVC} \quad D = \frac{R}{1 - \frac{AVC}{p}} \quad (12)$$

Applying Equations 4 and 10, the operating leverage at point „C” can be determined:

$$L = 1 + \frac{FC}{Pr} = 1 + \frac{FC}{V - VC - FC} = 1 + \frac{FC}{p \cdot q - AVC \cdot q - FC} = 1 + \frac{FC}{\frac{p \cdot FC - AVC \cdot FC}{q(1-R)-AVC} - FC} =$$

$$1 + \frac{FC \cdot p \cdot (1-R) - AVC}{FC \cdot (p - AVC - p(1-R) - AVC)} = 1 + \frac{p(1-R) - AVC}{p - p(1-R)} = \frac{p - p(1-R) + p(1-R) - AVC}{p - p(1-R)} = \frac{p - AVC}{p \cdot R}$$

$$L = \frac{1 - \frac{AVC}{p}}{R} \quad (13)$$

Considering that the normative value of return on sales is 0.2, the equations of the optimal financial safety margin (D_o) and optimal operating leverage (L_o) at point „C” take the form:

$$D_o = \frac{0.2}{1 - \frac{AVC}{p}} \quad (14)$$

$$L_o = \frac{1 - \frac{AVC}{p}}{0.2} \quad (15)$$

The optimal values of the analyzed indicators demonstrated the condition of production and level of economic security of enterprise.

Proposed equations for calculating indicators of operational activities for determining the level of economic security are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Formulas for calculating indicators of operational activities for determining the level of economic security in production

Indicators	Point A	Point B	Point C
Production volume, q	$q_{kp} = \frac{FC}{p}$	$q_{min} = \frac{FC}{p - AVC}$	$q_o = \frac{FC}{q(1 - R_v) - AVC}$
Financial safety margin, D	$D_{kp} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{p}{AVC}}$	$D = \frac{q - q_{min}}{q} = 0$	$D_o = \frac{R_p}{1 - \frac{AVC}{p}}$
Operating leverage, L	$L_{kp} = 1 - \frac{p}{AVC}$	$L = \frac{1}{D}$	$L_o = \frac{p - AVC}{R_p \cdot p}$

Source: Ianioglo⁵

By applying the presented equations and taking into account the current values of these indicators, the actual level of economic security of production can be identified on example of agricultural enterprise „Iri-Carmen” SRL (Table 2).

Table 2. Indicators of the level of economic security in the production of main agricultural crops at „Iri-Carmen” SRL, 2016.

a) depending on the crops yield

Indicators	Wheat	Corn	Sunflower
Fixed costs, lei/ha (FC)	2670.0	4135.5	5996.0
Average variable costs, lei/q (AVC)	94.9	93.3	113.5
Actual yield (q)	44.2	36.4	28.7
Selling price of products, lei/q (p)	235.0	208.9	631.2
Critical yield (q _{kp})	11.4	19.8	9.5

⁵ Ianioglo, A. Комплексная система обеспечения экономической безопасности предприятий [The comprehensive system of ensuring economic security of enterprises]. Monograph; Comrat State University, Scientific Research Center „Progress”. Comrat: B.i. (Tipogr. „Centrografic”), 2017. 161 p.

Minimum yield (q_{\min})	19.1	35.8	11.6
Optimum yield (q_o)	28.7	56.0	15.3
<i>Level of security</i>	high	medium	high

b) depending on the values of the financial safety margin

Indicators	Wheat	Corn	Sunflower
Critical financial safety margin (D_{kp})	-67.69	-80.7	-21.9
Optimal financial safety margin (D_o)	33.5	36.1	24.4
Actual financial safety margin (D)	56.9	1.7	59.6
<i>Level of security</i>	high	medium	high

c) depending on the values of the operating leverage

Indicators	Wheat	Corn	Sunflower
Critical operating leverage (L_{kp})	-1.5	-1.2	-4.6
Optimal operating leverage (L_o)	3.0	2.8	4.1
Actual operating leverage (L)	1.8	58.2	1.7
<i>Level of security</i>	high	medium	high

Source: calculated based on the forms 7 and 9 AIC of „Iri-Carmen” SRL, 2016

Analysis of indicators of operating activity in the production of crops by the example of „Iri-Carmen” SRL in 2016 showed that the enterprise reached a high level of economic security in the production of wheat and sunflower. The most vulnerable was the cultivation of corn.

There was proposed the method for analyzing the indicators of operating activities that has a practical importance in assessing the level of economic security. The analysis identified four levels of economic security: critical, low, medium, and high. The

critical level shows the riskiness of the business, while the high level indicates that enterprises obtain necessary profit for further development. One or all indicators may be applicable as they are interconnected and show the current level of security. Indicators of operating activity allow specialists to identify reserves for improving technology and increasing production efficiency to maximize profits. Therefore, the proposed method is important in determining directions of improving the economic security of an enterprise.

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